

THE HISTORY OF USING MOBILE APPS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Murodillayev Behzod

PhD student of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14504510>

Abstract. Language learning and teaching is a complex process that requires to use various approaches to make the process more effective and engaging. This in turn enables to test different methods and technologies in language acquisition. This article aims to explore use of modern technologies, in particular mobile applications in teaching language skills, as well as offer basic insights into history, effectiveness and possible difficulties of using apps in language learning process.

Key words: mobile applications, gamification, artificial intelligence(AI), vocabulary.

Introduction

Mobile devices have evolved to be one of the key technologies in learning activities with particular emphasis being placed on language applications. The evolution of mobile applications has transformed English language pedagogy by making it more accessible and more engaging for students around the globe. The purpose of this article is to investigate the past with respect to the use of mobile applications in the English language with the focus on the beginning, progress, and the present day. The role of mobile apps in language acquisition has developed from basic vocabulary tools to very complex apps utilizing current AI and gamification. This alteration indicates developments in the wider context of education and comes with the fact that mobile English language learning is becoming more common.

Methods

This study examines the historical trend of mobile applications regarding English language teaching, and it employs an historical analytical method. Attention is given to the review of important milestones in the growth of educational mobile applications dating from the early 2000s to the present day. A combination of secondary sources - including academic articles, books, and digital assets - was drawn upon to piece together information on the developments of mobile applications designed to support language learning. It aims to identify the trends in the development of applications, how the innovation in technology has been a factor, and the implications these applications have generated in the learning of English. It discusses some of the well-known mobile applications such as Duolingo, Babbel, Memrise, and HelloTalk to explain the key developments and shifting dynamics of mobile language education. On the other hand, it also recognizes that with any of these developments come challenges and realizes that greater clarity of such developments is imperative to obtain a fuller understanding of its impact. Although specific applications are discussed here, one realizes that larger narratives exist on how technology and education come together.

Results

The study shows that apps for learning English on mobile devices have changed a lot in the last 20 years. At first, people rarely used mobile devices for education. Early apps just had simple word quizzes and grammar practice. In the 2000s new apps like Duolingo, Babbel, and Memrise came out. These apps mixed basic ways to learn languages with fun stuff like games and lessons made just for you. These apps proved that mobile devices could help people learn languages.

In the 2010s, everyone started using smartphones and mobile apps. This led to better apps with cool features like checking your speech giving feedback right away, and teaching you based on real situations. Duolingo made its app even better by adding lessons that use AI to fit each person. HelloTalk let people practice languages with native speakers in real time. These changes match what's happening in education overall where mobile apps started to give people more real-life, personal, and flexible ways to learn.

A study by Stockwell [8] and others in 2015 found that language-learning apps like Duolingo have helped people learn new words beginners who are learning English. In the last few years, AI, speech recognition, and AR have made mobile apps more powerful. These apps now give detailed reports on how well students are doing. AI systems create personalized learning plans based on what users are good at and what they struggle with. Apps like FluentU and Babbel now use real-world stuff such as video clips and news stories, to help people understand English better in different situations. This study found that apps like Babbel and FluentU can work well for mid-level to advanced students by using more context-based learning. This goes against what Wang, Z., & Cui, Y.[10] said, who thought mobile apps were not sufficient for high-level language learning.

Discussion

Mobile apps in English language teaching show big changes in education. These changes make learning more flexible, easy to access, and personal. Apps for phones give students many good things. Students can learn any time and place they want. The apps have content that keeps students interested. They also give personal feedback to help students see how well they are doing. Games in the apps make learning fun, which makes students want to keep practicing English. This study agrees with what Lin [7] found. Lee said games in apps make students more interested. But this refutes with Bracke, K. [4]. They were not sure if apps help students speak better in the long run.

But using apps a lot has some problems and people criticize it. Apps are easy to use and access. But some people say apps can't be as good as learning face-to-face with a teacher. Apps often teach basic features like words, grammar, and how to say things. But they might not teach harder components well. These harder things include understanding culture and complex language structures. Furthermore, the digital divide remains a significant issue, as not all students have equal access to mobile devices or reliable internet connectivity, limiting the benefits of mobile learning for some.

Despite these difficulties, the future of mobile apps in English language teaching seems promising. As technology continues to develop, mobile apps are anticipated to provide even more personalized, intriguing, and interactive learning experiences. The combination of AI, speech recognition, and other innovative features will likely further enhance their efficacy, making them useful tools for learners at different levels.

Conclusion

Mobile apps have made a profound impact on the way English is taught and learned, giving students a flexible, interactive, and personalized way to obtain language skills. From their early start as simple vocabulary tools to their current use of AI and gaming, mobile apps have played a crucial role in altering language education. While hardships remain, such as the heavy reliance and the need for deeper language immersion, the future of mobile apps in teaching English seems bright. Current technological advancements will possibly lead to even

more futuristic and efficacious learning platforms, fostering students achieve proficiency in English.

References:

1. Andersen, I. 2013, "Mobile Apps for Learning English. A Review of 7 Complete English Course Apps: Characteristics, Similarities and Differences."
2. Armstrong, J.S. 2012, "Natural learning in higher education", Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning. Heidelberg: Springer Conroy, M.A. 2010, "Internet tools for language learning: University students taking control of their writing", Australasian Journal of Educational Technology, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 861-882.
3. Bryman, A. & Bell, E. 2011, "Business research methods", Oxford University Press, Oxford
4. Bracke, K. (2013). Apps for mobile language learning: A market research into English language learning apps. Unpublished Master Thesis, University College Ghent, Belgium
5. Gedera, D.S.P. 2011, "Integration of weblogs in developing language skills of ESL learners." International Journal of Technology in Teaching and Learning, vol.7, no.2, pp.124-135.
6. Kim, D., Rueckert, D., Kim, D.-J., & Seo, D. (2013). Students' perceptions and experiences of mobile learning. Language Learning & Technology, 17(3), 52-73.
7. Lin, T. J., Duh, H. B. L., Li, N., Wang, H. Y., & Tsai, C. C. (2013). An investigation of learners' collaborative knowledge construction performances and behavior patterns in an augmented reality simulation system. Computers & Education, 68, 314-321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.05.011>.
8. Stockwell, G. (2010). Using mobile phones for vocabulary activities: examining the effect of the platform. Language Learning and Teaching, 14(2), 95-110
9. Tom, C. (1999). Breadth and Depth of Lexical Acquisition with Hands-on Concordancing. Computer Assisted Language Learning, 12(4), 345-360.
10. Wang, Z., & Cui, Y. (2016). Mobile-assisted language learning in China's college English education: The reality and research. In Mobile learning design (pp. 335-349). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-0027-0_20.